

Arkitektbron An optimized pedestrian bridge

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ABSTRACT

In Gothenburg, a new pedestrian bridge is needed. The main structure consists of two steel arches which provide two intermediate supports to the deck which is made of Fiber Reinforced Polymer (FRP). The design of the bridge is optimized to reduce the material needed and to create an elegant shape, but the light materials also decrease the loads on the substructure to minimize the number of piles needed for the foundation due to bad soil conditions.

The design of the main steel structure was the responsibility of SYSTRA AB in Sweden, while the FRP deck was designed by Royal HaskoningDHV in the Netherlands. The main design challenge met was the dynamic behaviour of the bridge due to human induced vibrations. Besides the technical challenges, there were also challenges to find a reliable and efficient way to for the companies to collaborate while in two different countries. To accommodate these challenges, it was decided to create a parametric coordination model, in Rhino/Grasshopper, from which the design and calculation models were generated. This coordination model ensured that at any time both companies had an up-to-date version of the model. This turned out crucial as the dynamic behaviour of the bridge was significantly influenced by the interaction between the steel and FRP components. Due to the parametric nature of the model, a variation study was possible, where a total of 200 variants were produced to find an optimal design. Combining FRP and steel became an elegant solution, incorporating both a conventional material and a newer one, the result is illustrated in *Fig. 1*.

Keywords: FRP, parametric, collaboration, pedestrian bridge

Fig. 1. Illustration of the pedestrian bridge over the canal

1 INTRODUCTION

In Gothenburg, for the first time in 100 years, a new bridge over the canal is being built. It is a pedestrian bridge designed by architect Malin Mirsch of SYSTRA AB and the client is the city of Gothenburg.

Due to poor soil conditions in the area, a light Fiber Reinforced Polymer (FRP) deck was chosen. FRP is not a very common material in Sweden and therefore Dennis Schakel, who worked at SYSTRA AB at the time, contacted Kees van IJselmuiden at Royal HaskoningDHV in the Netherlands where many FRP bridges have been built. Both companies were enthusiastic about designing this bridge and the collaboration was quickly established. At the outset of the project, the difficulties of designing a bridge involving two companies in different countries and potential dynamic interaction were recognized. A concerted effort was made from the start to devise an efficient process for collaboration. The resultant project is elaborated on in this paper.

2 ARCHITECTURAL CONCEPT

The primary focus has been developing an optimized structure with a clear synergy between architecture and construction. An optimized structure also minimizes its environmental footprint. The pedestrian bridge, as designed, spans 35 meters with a width of 4 meters and a mid-span elevation of 2,4 meters above the waterline.

Arkitektbron is included in the implementation decision for the Urban Development of Haga Station, part of the Västlänken project in Gothenburg, which the Municipal Council made on January 31, 2019. The design work for the bridge has been ongoing iteratively since 2020, with several reviews involving the Gothenburg City Architect and other city representatives.

The bridge will serve primarily as a pedestrian bridge, acting as a key link between Haga and the city centre. Cyclists are encouraged to commute via other nearby bridges across the canal. The aim is for the bridge to become part of a more intricate and connected pedestrian network in the city centre while enhancing the opportunity for Gothenburg residents to commute and enjoy the city's diverse riverside spaces and destinations.

The current detailed development plan stipulates a relatively small area for the pedestrian bridge and comes with numerous specifications. The plan development description guides the design of the Arkitektbron, stating that the bridge's design should consider the historical environment of its surroundings.

The new pedestrian bridge should be designed thoughtfully, aligning its form with the well-integrated historical environment of the canal space while maintaining an uninterrupted water reflection. It should harmonize with the visual context of the canal space, both with the distinctive lattice works of Rosenlundsbron and Viktoriabron and with the southern and northern sides of the canal space, reflecting different historical functions. Additionally, there are requirements for clearance height and protection of nearby trees.

In the design of Arkitektbron, various perspectives have been considered, such as those from nearby bridges, the promenade through Kungsparken and along Sahlgrensgratan, as well as from Haga Station or Arkitektgratan. The bridge is situated in an open urban space, visible from all directions.

Fig. 2. Bridge dimensions (in millimetres)

The only supports needed for the bridge, are two strategically placed steel arches connecting both sides. The steel arches are fixed at both ends and divide the FRP deck into three spans over the water: 11,8+12,0+11,8 meters (Fig. 2). The arches spring from the park's slope and neatly land on the canal wall on the other side. They carry the bridge deck from a park environment to an urban environment, a transition reflected in its form. This principle reinforces the architectural and functional differences between the two sides. The bridge maintains the greatest possible distance from the uninterrupted water reflection, and its two supports accommodate the different conditions of the two urban spaces. The minimalistic design of the bridge features no unnecessary ornaments or frills, blending into the historical context while exuding a modern feel. The supports integrate seamlessly into the surroundings on both sides, without adding any extra elements.

The ambition was to make the bridge deck thinner than the arch, emphasizing the hierarchy that the arch supports the deck. Steel was deemed a suitable material for designing bridges of this span range and allows for a wide range of designs. Steel, in terms of its form and texture, also ties into the existing material palette of the canal space. The bridge deck consists of a web-core sandwich panel, built up from multiple FRP laminates and a foam core. The foam core is considered non-structural, and its stiffness and strength are not considered.

The dynamic interplay between the arch and the bridge deck is accentuated by giving them different colors, which will appear differently pronounced throughout the day. The supporting steel arch takes the lead role and is highlighted with a red hue, contrasting with the park's greenery and the dark water. The earthy color is warm and distinct, found on several buildings in the vicinity, such as the window frames of *Gamla Latin*. The green color connects the bridge to other nearby canal bridges, extending the green spatial continuity over the water. The railing, subordinate to the arch, aligns with other city bridges with its green color, and its detailed fillings enhance the details for pedestrians.

3 OPTIMIZATION AND COLLABORATION

From the early stages of project design, the collaboration and efficiency of coordination between the companies was a critical factor determining the success of the project. The workflow had to allow for easy access to the models for both parties and provide a high degree of flexibility to accommodate structural challenges and design modifications. To achieve this, a parametric model script was developed in Grasshopper, which offered both accessibility and flexibility to changes. Therefore, it was decided to create such a script for the Arkitektbron and connect it to the drawing software TEKLA and Finite Element Analysis (FEA) software SOFiSTiK. Workflow is shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Workflow for the Arkitektbron project, where the coordination model forms the centre of the design process.

The deck structure was modelled in its entirety, incorporating both steel and FRP components. This was necessary as the interaction between the materials had an impact on the dynamic properties of the structure. In SOFiSTiK this connection was made by modelling a beam at the bottom of the deck that serves as a support.

In the drawings that were created in Tekla, this connection is visualised and shown in *fig. 4*. A section of that part is also shown in figure 4, where the structure of the FRP deck is drawn.

Fig. 4. a) Cross section bridge deck, b) Tekla model

Finding the optimal design for a hybrid bridge structure through manual iteration proved difficult due to the complex nature of vibration checks. However, the use of a parametric script enabled a variant analysis with more possibilities than conventional methods. By setting ranges for important design parameters, over 200 potential design configurations were generated. Their performances were quantified based on both static and dynamic checks for the hybrid pedestrian bridge.

For static checks, deflection and buckling of the steel support were the governing factors, while stresses in construction elements were less limiting. For dynamic checks, eigenfrequencies were calculated and compared with pedestrian load excitation frequency, and the structural acceleration of the bridge was determined to check pedestrian comfort. The processed data was then gathered into a design exploring process, led by the structural engineer and designer, to ensure no choices were made without their expertise.

During this design exploring process, the steel main beams were also able to be optimized. The governing design check were the buckling of the beams due to high normal forces and a slender design of the beams. The buckling of the beam has been a critical point in the design and using SOFiSTiK the exact critical buckling lengths were calculated as well as critical flexural and torsional buckling forces. The design of the steel beams optimizes the use of materials by integrating the use of higher-grade steel (S460) where needed, resulting in a slim and efficient configuration.

The height of the beam on the quay wall side was also critical. Due to thermal-induced displacement at the top of the beam, a large bending moment is induced when the beam extends beyond the rigid connection to the substructure. A higher beam would be beneficial due to the lower angular rotation of the beam. This would however block the view of the pedestrians when walking on the bridge. To ensure a balance between the view of the pedestrians and the structural capacity it was chosen for a bigger structural height of the vertical part of the main beam.

4 DYNAMIC BEHAVIOUR

While the weight of the bridge and its associated loads decreased significantly, using FRP, the decreased stiffness of the deck introduced new challenges in its dynamic behaviour. This constraint proved to be one of the major factors in developing a viable design.

Dynamic properties are an important consideration in the design and analysis of bridges, particularly for bridges that are subjected to pedestrian and bicycle traffic. The dynamic behaviour of the bridge is affected by the properties of the steel beam in combination with the FRP deck. The dynamic properties of the steel beam and FRP sandwich deck bridge were analysed using a FEA in SOFiSTiK.

The SOFiSTiK Advanced Solution Engine (ASE) has a module to calculate the natural frequencies of a structure. The first two natural frequencies for the Arkitektbron are 2,96 Hz and 5,51 Hz. Research by Fieldmann et al. (1), concludes that significant vibrations of eigenfrequencies footbridges do not occur due to the second harmonics, only the first eigenfrequency is compared to the frequencies of the pedestrian loadings. According to the Human Induced Vibrations Of Steel Structures (HIVOSS) guideline (2), the reduction factor for the first harmonic approaches 0 for frequencies above 2,3 HZ. For the second harmonic the natural frequency of 2,96 Hz. results in a reduction factor of 0,125.

Besides the eigenfrequencies, also the human induced acceleration of the structure is also checked. As a result, the damping ratio is relevant. The damping is a weighted ratio of the damping of the steel structure and the FRP deck. The upper bound damping ratio (1,5 %) of the steel bridges is used as a lower bound value for the Arkitektbron, as this is the case for the steel bridges with timber decks (3). Measured damping ratios of FRP bridges (4) are 2,0 to 2,5 % on average. From this a damping ratio between 1,5 % and 2,0 % can be considered. However, due to the high variations mentioned, a conservative value of 1,0 % is chosen for the Arkitektbron calculations. For the variant analysis, a quick assessment had to be made of the systems accelerations. This is done by simplifying the bridge as a Single Degree OF Freedom (SDOF) system and calculate the maximum acceleration.

This calculation is done according to the formula for maximum acceleration for structures, obtained from the HIVOSS guideline:

$$a_{max} = \frac{p^*}{m^*} \frac{1}{2\xi} \quad (1)$$

where p^* is the generalised load,
 m^* is the generalised (modal) mass,
 ξ is the structural damping ratio.

Fig. 5. Beam height related to comfort check.

Based on the comfort limit of 0,7 m/s² of the HIVOSS guideline, the unity checks can be computed for all the variants (Fig. 5). The generalised modal mass was obtained from the SOFiSTiK calculations for each variant and the generalised load is approached by taking of the total 2/π distributed loads. These calculations revealed that pedestrian comfort with regards to acceleration were one of the key design drivers. The results were straightforward to interpret, with initial manual variants showing the unity check for pedestrian comfort increased as the beam height decreased.

This behaviour was visualized, as shown in Fig. 6, using a design explorer. The beam height is plotted against the unity check for pedestrian comfort based on accelerations, where each dot represents a variant. This showed that a lower stiffness of the support beam would mobilize more of the FRP deck and thereby more resistance against acceleration of the bridge.

After the SDOF analysis of the accelerations for all variants, eventually a time step analysis is also conducted for the final design. This dynamic analysis had a computational time of around 2 hours showing the result of a maximum acceleration of 0,66 m/s² which validated the assumptions that were made for the variants.

Fig. 6. Design Explorer (Left axis 200 variants, right axis's dynamic checks, between beam and deck dimensions).

The design explorer's filtering feature was used to eliminate all unity checks above 1. From the complete design explorer results data depicted in Figure 6, the feasible designs could be filtered. Based on unity checks that are coupled to the parametric model, a selection was made of only feasible designs. The final design featured an FRP deck thickness of 480 mm and a beam height of 550 mm, resulting in pedestrian comfort unity checks of 0,98 and a total displacement of 37 mm, well below the limit. In this design the stiffnesses of both the steel and FRP materials are distributed such that the resistance to pedestrian induced acceleration of the bridge is minimized. The total mass of the structure became 49,8 tons.

Once the structure's design was completed, the coordination model was linked to Tekla drawing software using the Grasshopper plug-in, allowing for the extraction of up-to-date drawings.

5 COMPARISON BETWEEN FRP AND STEEL

The design of the bridge is a good example of how a construction can be optimized using the right material for the right purpose. Steel and FRP complement each other and the result is a slender bridge with a reduced carbon footprint.

A secondary model has been generated to illustrate the distinctions in material application when compared to a conventional steel bridge. A feasibility study was completed using a deck with two side girders of HE450A profiles with a steel plate on top, replacing the FRP parts. This plate was strengthened using steel transversal beams every 60 cm. An overview of a part of the FEM model is shown in *Fig. 7*.

Figure 7. FEM model of the full steel deck.

The steel variant is not optimised, but only created to compare material usage on a basic level. This variant is designed based on similar deflections, while buckling is not considered. It can be observed that the total weight of the deck ranges from 16,1 tonnes for the FRP deck to 33,0 tonnes (*Fig. 8*), with the full steel deck as shown in Table 1 below.

Table 1. Comparison of material usage

	FRP deck [tonnes]	Full steel deck [tonnes]
Deck plate	13,8	12,4
Troughs and transversal beams	2,3	11,8
Longitudinal beams	-	8,8
Total deck	16,1	33,0

Fig. 8. Deck material comparison.

The use of a steel deck contributing to an increase in weight would have negative effects on the rest of the bridge. Due to the high utility ratio for buckling, the main beams would buckle under the extra load of the deck. To avoid this the dimensions of the beam would need to be increased. This would then result in a new dynamic analysis to see if the accelerations are still within the limits.

Another impact would be increased loads on the footplates of the main beam and the bolted connection. These connections would also need to be increased to be able to withstand the higher bending moments.

The decrease in material usage results in a few distinctions in terms of its environmental implications. In this comparison, the differences between the full steel and hybrid steel-FRP design are compared on a qualitative level. The differences are:

1. The material savings can result in a direct reduction in environmental impact in the manufacturing process.
2. The soil conditions were poor in the region of the bridge project. With the total weight of the bridge decreasing with respect to the full steel bridge, the FRP variant is able to reduce the amount of foundation piles. An increased load on the substructure will result in an increased amount of reinforcement within the substructure. For the pile foundation this would result in a need for more piles and consequently, would require a bigger slab. This results in more concrete, reinforcement and a bigger sheet pile wall needed during the construction stage.
3. The maintenance of a FRP deck is less frequent and involves less coatings, compared to a steel deck.
4. The protective layer on top of the bridge deck in the steel variant needs to protect the steel plate against corrosion. In case of damage or deterioration, the full layer should be renewed. For the FRP variant, this layer is only for grip and in case of damage it could be repaired locally which reduces the impact on the environment.

Besides the advantages of applying a deck of FRP, it should also be noted that the emissions per ton of used material, especially regarding CO₂, are higher for FRP compared to steel. Recent developments like biobased resins can reduce this difference. An advanced life cycle analysis should be conducted, considering all the project and structure specifics, to make a detailed comparison in total environmental impact of the materialisation.

6 FURTHER DEVELOPMENT AND LESSONS LEARNED

In the vicinity, another pedestrian bridge, Kaponjärbron, was previously considered but unfortunately was never realized. It was mainly constructed using FRP, which made it very complicated with a difficult-to-access central support near the water surface. The project also encountered other technical difficulties and site-related obstacles. Therefore, the focus in the design of the bridge has been on feasibility.

A primary emphasis was placed on the constructability of the final design. The bridge is located in the center of Gothenburg and transport routes are limited for larger elements. Besides the transport of elements, the amount of construction work on site was also to be limited. The aim has been to avoid painting the steel structure on site. Therefore, bolted connections are used over welded connections where possible. This will result in more work in a controlled environment and less on site.

The location itself has historical value with many old structures that cannot be damaged during construction. One of the abutments is also replacing the 100-year-old stone quay wall, this was solved by using the old quay wall stones to use as surface material of the abutment. The same abutment is also located above an old fortification. The remains of this fortification (See *fig. 9*) are unclear and can cause troubles executing the pile foundation and sheet pile wall. This is solved by drilling steel piles instead of hammering concrete piles.

Fig. 9. Plan showing the remaining fortification.

Concluding from the project of the Arkitektbron, the creation of a central coordination model enabled the teams to collaborate on a single, centralized model. Because it was established from the start that the model would be subject to large variations and should therefore be parametric, a large number of variants could be efficiently created.

The design exploration process revealed some conclusions that would have been difficult to find using manual design procedures. For example, the observation that decreasing the support beam height resulted in better resistance to pedestrian induced acceleration of the structure was made possible by examining the variants in the design explorer. The final design proved that a hybrid structure was able to significantly reduce the weight of the Arkitektbron compared to a full steel bridge.

Ultimately, the parametric process created the possibility to go from a basic design to a detailed verified design in collaboration between companies. The parametric model, as a single source of truth, was always available and could be extended for each purpose, such as adding checks for dynamic pedestrian loads and utilizing a design explorer to compare a large number of variants.

7 REFERENCES

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